

ABBOT WOLFGANG JONER VON KAPPEL (1471–1531)

A Practitioner of the Reformation¹

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Memories of the Reformation still very often focus on individual figures – in the case of the Zurich Reformation, mostly Huldrych Zwingli, and increasingly also his successor Heinrich Bullinger². In the wake of growing attention to female figures, the 500th anniversary of the handover of the Fraumünster in 2024 provided an opportunity to focus more attention on the last abbess of the Fraumünster, Katharina von Zimmern³.

What these figures have in common is that the city of Zurich itself was their primary sphere of activity. In contrast, the introduction and establishment of the Reformation in the Zurich countryside have been far less studied. When they have been studied, however, scholars mainly focused on the friction between the Zurich city authorities, who sought to extend their control over the countryside, and the rural communities, who insisted on preserving their traditional rights⁴. Against this

¹ This is the translation of an article first published in *Zwingliana* 52, 2025, 9–44. As the process leading to this article includes a paper given in the research seminar of the Institut d'histoire de la Réformation in Geneva on 28 October 2024, it is only just that this translation appears in the IHR's bulletin.

² For an overview of trends in research on the Zurich Reformation, see Tobias Jammerthal, *Neuere Forschungen zur Zürcher Reformationsgeschichte*, in *Historisches Jahrbuch* 144, 2024, 392–412.

³ See most recently, in particular, Christine Christ-von Wedel, *Die Äbtissin, der Söldnerführer und ihre Töchter. Katharina von Zimmern im politischen Spannungsfeld der Reformationszeit*, unter Mitarbeit von Irene Gysel, Jeanne Pestalozzi und Marlis Stähli, Zurich 2020, and Irene Gysel, *Katharina von Zimmern. Flüchtlingskind, Äbtissin, Bürgerin von Zürich*, Zurich 2024. For further publications and general information on Katharina memorial, see the research report by Franziska Escher in *Zwingliana* 52, 2025, 223–241.

⁴ Paradigmatic examples include Ursula Kägi, *Die Aufnahme der Reformation in den ostschweizerischen Untertanengebieten – der Weg Zürichs zu einem obrigkeitlichen Kirchenregiment bis zum Frühjahr 1529*, Zurich 1972, and also the careful study by Peter Kamber, *Reformation als bäuerliche Revolution. Bildersturm, Klosterbesetzungen und Kampf gegen die Leibeigenschaft in Zürich zur Zeit der Reformation (1522–1525)*, Zurich 2010. Kamber himself reveals that he is strongly committed to Peter Blickle's approach to communal or parish reformation (summarised in: Peter Blickle, *Die Gemeindereformation. Die Menschen des 16. Jahrhunderts auf dem Weg zum Heil*, Munich 1987), which is important as a corrective to Bernd Moeller's focus on the urban centres of the Reformation (Bernd Moeller, *Reichsstadt und Reformation*, Gütersloh 1962), but which must

backdrop, the Reformation in the Zurich countryside appears primarily as an aspect of the early modern consolidation of power by the city magistrates at the expense of medieval communitarian models of society⁵. From the perspective of a church historian, this is surprising insofar as important actors in the early Zurich Reformation were representatives of church institutions *from the countryside*: hardly any account of the early 1520s omits the commander of the Knights Hospitaller in Küsnacht, Konrad Schmid⁶; the provost of the canons in Embrach, Heinrich Brennwald, appears repeatedly⁷, and the abbot of the Cistercian monastery in Kappel, Wolfgang Joner, known as Rüppli, also occupies an almost canonical place in accounts of the Zurich Reformation⁸.

face serious critical questions from a sociological, historical and theological perspective; see Andrea Strübind, *Eifriger als Zwingli. Die frühe Täuferbewegung in der Schweiz*, Berlin 2003, 79–119.

⁵ The most important objections to this overly schematic comparison are summarised by Strübind, *Eifriger als Zwingli*, 96–119.

⁶ See Karl Rudolf Hagenbach, *Geschichte der Reformation, vorzüglich in Deutschland und der Schweiz*, Leipzig 1870, 236, with reference to Johann Heinrich Hess, *Conrad Schmid*, Zurich 1825 (An die lernbegierige Zürcherische Jugend von der Gesellschaft auf der Chorherrenstube, 47); see since then Carl Christoph Bernoulli, *Zum Studiengang des Komthur Schmid*, in *Zwingliana* 1/17, 1904, 461–463; Emil Egli, *Komthur Schmid von Küsnacht*, in *Zwingliana* 2/3 (1906), 65–73; Werner Meyer, *Komthur Konrad Schmid von Küsnacht*, in *Der Grundriss* 7, 1945, 323–353; Gottfried W. Locher, *Die Zwinglische Reformation im Rahmen der europäischen Kirchengeschichte*, Göttingen/Zurich 1979, 132, 135, 576–580; Alfred Egli, *Komthur Konrad Schmid, ein Wegbereiter der Reformation*, in *Küsnachter Jahrbücher* 21, 1981, 30–48; Christoph A. Schweiss, *Die Johanniter-Komturei Küsnacht und ihr Komthur Konrad Schmid*, in *Jahrbest der Ritterhausgesellschaft Bubikon* 60, 1996, 12–35; Bruce Gordon, *The Swiss Reformation*, Manchester/New York 2002, 63, 158; Emidio Campi, *Die Reformation in Zürich*, in *Die schweizerische Reformation. Ein Handbuch*, ed. by id. and Amy Nelson Burnett, Zurich 2017, 276, 385; most recently see Beat Hänni and Ruth Jörg, *Konrad Schmid's Predigt von 1522 in Luzern. Ein früher Schlüsseltext der eidgenössischen Reformation*, in *Zwingliana* 50, 2023, 1–54, as well as Beat Hänni and Ruth Jörg (eds.), *Wenn Gott durch die Finger blinzelt. Konrad Schmid's Predigt von 1522 in Luzern – ein früher Schlüsseltext der schweizerischen Reformation*, Zurich 2023.

⁷ In classical accounts, he is usually mentioned in connection with the establishment of the «Mushaf»; see Rudolf Pfister, *Kirchengeschichte der Schweiz, vol. 2: Von der Reformation bis zum Zweiten Villmerger Krieg*, Zurich 1974, 41; Locher, *Reformation*, 139, 153; Campi, *Reformation*, 88; Gordon, *Swiss Reformation*, 65. For his career, see Robert Hoppeler, *Zur Biographie des Embracher Propstes Heinrich Brennwald*, in *Zwingliana* 3, 1920, 509–514; id., *Das Kollegiatstift St. Peter in Embrach*, in *MAGZ* 29, 1921, 3–25; 29–78, 72–77; id., *Nachtrag zur Brennwald-Biographie*, in *Zwingliana* 4/2, 1921, 51; id., *On Heinrich Brennwald*, in *Zwingliana* 4/10, 1925, 319; Emil Stauber, *Ein Beitrag zum Lebensbild von Heinrich Brennwald*, in *Zwingliana* 4/9, 1925, 284.

⁸ Pfister, *Kirchengeschichte*, 67, 177; Locher, *Reformation*, 139, 423, 534, 577; Campi, *Reformation*, 104. The basis for most of this is Salomon Vögelin's account, which draws heavily on Bullinger's history of the Reformation: Wolfgang Joner Rüppli, *1471–1531. Abt zu Kappel*, Zurich 1830 (Neujahrsblatt zum Besten des Waisenhaus Zürich, 52), the brief account by Ernst Leisi, *Rüppli, von – 2. Wolfgang Joner*, in *HBLJ*, vol. 5, Neuchâtel 1929, 744, and the comments by Emil Egli, note 1 on *Wolfgang Joner's letter to Zwingli, 6 October 1529 (?)*, in *Huldreich Zwingli's Sämtliche Werke*, ed. by Emil Egli et al., vol. 10, Leipzig 1929, 314 [no. 924]; see in particular Ulrich Gäbler, *Einleitung*, in *Heinrich Bullinger Briefwechsel [HBBW]*, vol. 1, Zurich 1973, 48, note 1; Magdalen Bless-Grabher, *Rüppli Wolfgang*, in *Historical Dictionary of Switzerland [HLS]*, vol. 10, Basel 2011, 694, and more recently also Hans Brauchli, *Wolfgang Joner, 1471–1531. Frauenfeld, Abt des Klosters Kappel und Freund Zwinglis*, in *Thurgauer Abnegalerie*, Weinfelden 2003, 112–115.

It is the latter who will be examined once again in what follows. The guiding consideration here is that Abbot Wolfgang Joner can be seen as representative of a group of actors who will be provisionally referred to as *practitioners of the Reformation*: clergy who held a somewhat senior position at the local or regional level within the late medieval church system and who decided not to resist the changes to the church system brought about by the Reformation, but to shape them through their own participation. As the example of Wolfgang Joner shows, it would be too simplistic to cite purely political or economic reasons for this; rather, it can be assumed that they agreed with the theological impulses of the Reformation. However, Reformation practitioners are less distinguished by their own theological writings than by the fact that they repeatedly appear in the files, minutes and reports of their contemporaries when it came to preparing and implementing changes in church practice. This does not deny that they did not also have their own theological profile – but given the available sources, it is much more challenging to discern it than in the case of, e.g., Zwingli or Bullinger.

The following observations on Abbot Wolfgang Joner as a reformatory practitioner are preceded by some aspects of his career. The concluding remarks are intended as an invitation to further reflection⁹.

1 Wolfgang Joner's career

1.1 Until the election as abbot

Abbot Wolfgang comes from a good family: when he was born in Frauenfeld in 1471, his father was the mayor there. The family is considered to be long-established in Thurgau: since the 13th century, the Joner, known as Rüppli, have been vassals of the bishops of Constance and the abbots of St. Gallen; Wolfgang's father Hans is Lord of Kesikon and Islikon¹⁰, Wolfgang's brother, also named Hans, is documented as a member of the Council of Three in Frauenfeld in 1506, and from 1512 to 1524 he holds the office of mayor every two years¹¹. It was not unusual for children from the upper echelons of urban society in terms of profession, income or

⁹ This essay is based on lectures given by the author on 28 October 2024 at the Institut d'histoire de la Réformation in Geneva, on 3 November 2024 at Kappel Monastery and on 19 May 2024 at the annual meeting of the Zwingli Association. I would like to express my sincere thanks to all discussion partners for their insightful questions and suggestions.

¹⁰ See Vögelin, *Wolfgang Joner*, 3.

¹¹ See Leisi, *Rüpplin*, 744; Gäbler, *Einleitung*, 48, note 4.

origin, to be sent to monasteries – the connection of the medieval church and its institutions with these circles was a tradition; children from such families often held positions within the church that were comparable to those of their siblings in secular life. This was also the case with Wolfgang Joner: By 1506, he was already custodian in Kappel, in 1509 he was elected prior and in 1519 he became abbot¹². The date of his entry into the Cistercian monastery in Kappel is not entirely certain: it is documented that he was a member of the convent in Kappel at the time of the great fire at the abbey on 15 January 1493¹³. When the Zurich Council granted him a so-called *Leibgeding*, a kind of pension, at the beginning of 1531, the Council's decision refers to over forty years of service¹⁴, which suggests that he entered the monastery around 1490/1491. However, the further circumstances of his career until he assumed higher offices within the Kappel convent are unclear. In particular, there is no evidence that Wolfgang Joner attended university or received any other higher education. On the other hand, it can be proven that he gained experience in the pastoral field: the Central Library in Zurich has an undated copy of the oath taken by a « Frater Wolphgang Ruplin Cappelanus¹⁵ » on the occasion of his appointment as chaplain in Merenschwand – the Kappel monastery had held ecclesial rights there since 1389 and the parish church of Merenschwand had been incorporated into the Kappel convent in 1406¹⁶. Contrary to customary practice, Pope Boniface IX had permitted the Cistercians of Kappel to send curates from amongst their own conventuals to Merenschwand¹⁷. In Wolfgang's case, this appears to have been exercised for the St. Mary's chaplaincy¹⁸, which had been founded in 1332 by the Lords of Hünenberg. However, it is not clear when and by whom he received the

¹² See Bless-Grabher, *Rüpplin*, 744.

¹³ See Peter Simler and Heinrich Bullinger, *Annales sive Chronicon Coenobii Capell*, in Johann Jacob Simler, *Sammlung alter und neuer Urkunden zur Beleuchtung der Kirchen-Geschichte, vornehmlich des Schweizerlandes*, vol. 2, Zurich 1767, 397–455, here 443: « Videre hanc calamitatem [the monastery fire] miserabilem Stempflius ac Schönenbergius abbates, Johannes Murer, qui prioris fungebatur officio, Rodolphum Burckardi, Ulricus Koler, Joannes Kleger, Antonius Hass, Johannes Vittel, Leonhartus Aebly, Joannes Oefely, Ulricus Wüst, Joannes Landolt, Joannes Conradi, *Wolphgangus Jonerus*, who was then newly initiated into the order » (emphasis added by T. J.).

¹⁴ « Als dann der erwürdig, unser lieber, getrüwer burger, H. Wolfgang Rupli, abt oder verwalter unsers huses zuo Cappel, uns demüetigklich angesuoht, in, in bedenkung siner getrüwen diensten, müeg, sorg und arbeit, so er nun ob den vierzig jaren her mit versehung der canzel und anderer ämpter, ouch getrüwer hushab, bi und in demselben hus gehept » (Emil Egli, *Actensammlung zur Geschichte der Zürcher Reformation in den Jahren 1519–1533*, Zurich 1879, 744 [no. 1735]).

¹⁵ Zentralbibliothek Zurich [ZB], Ms 50.19, 112r.

¹⁶ See Anton Largiadèr, *Die Papsturkunden des Staatsarchivs Zürich von Innozenz III. bis Martin V. Ein Beitrag zum Consimentum Helveticum*, Zurich 1963, no. 148; see Magdalen Bless-Grabher, *Zisterzienserkloster Kappel*, in *Helvetia Sacra*, vol. 3/3.1, Bern 1982, 246–289, here 257.

¹⁷ Privilege of Pope Boniface IX dated 1 January 1400 (see Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 155).

¹⁸ See Georg Germann, *Die Kunstdenkmäler des Kantons Aargau, vol. 5: Der Bezirk Muri*, Basel 1967, 154.

higher orders that qualified him for this position. If the canonical age requirements laid down by the Council of Vienne in 1311/1312 had been observed in Merenschwand, Joner could have become chaplain in Merenschwand in 1496 at the earliest¹⁹. Although the chaplain had to vow to take up residence in Merenschwand and, regardless of this, to strictly obey his abbot, who was also free to remove the chaplain from his position and call him back to the monastery²⁰, Wolfgang Joner seems to have remained chaplain at the altar of St. Mary in Merenschwand even after taking on higher convent offices: According to the investiture records in the episcopal archives, it was not until February 1520 that his fellow monk Petrus Vottel was sworn in as his successor²¹.

1.2 Since the election

With his election as abbot of Kappel at the end of 1519, Wolfgang Joner became lord of the religious and economic centre of the surrounding area. This was true despite the fact that the monastery had been struggling with economic difficulties for some time²², that the abbey had suffered severe economic setbacks in the 15th century due to the devastation of the Old Zurich War in 1443 and the monastery fire of 1493²³, and that it had increasingly come under the influence and control of the up-and-coming city of Zurich²⁴. The abbot and convent of the Kappel monastery still owned extensive lands²⁵, exercised lower jurisdiction in a number of villages and

¹⁹ The minimum age for ordination was set at 25 in Vienne. If this provision had been applied in the case of Wolfgang Joner, he could not have been ordained before 1496 at the earliest. Unfortunately, the Constance investiture records only show that in 1491, Johannes Hunenberg, a member of the Kappel convent, was invested as successor to Ulrich Nerach after being presented by the abbot of Kappel (Manfred Krebs, *Die Investiturprotokolle der Diözese Konstanz aus dem 15. Jahrhundert* [Part 4], in *FDA* 70, 1950, 425–546, here 543); the next entry concerns Wolfgang Joner's successor (see note 21 below).

²⁰ « ibi habere residentiam corporalem, quae si habuerit, nihilominus in potestate abbatis erit, et quaecumque eius necessarius fuerit primus vel alius abbas, per ipsum revocare ad ministerium tunc debet sine omni contradictione parere, et praedictam caplaniam ad manus abbatis resignare » (ZB, Ms F 50.19, 112r).

²¹ Franz Hundsnurscher (ed.), *Die Investiturprotokolle der Diözese Konstanz aus dem 16. Jahrhundert, Teil 2: Lachen–Zwiefaltendorf*, Stuttgart 2008 (Veröffentlichungen der Kommission für Geschichtliche Landeskunde in Baden-Württemberg, Reihe A, 48/2), 583.

²² See Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 256.

²³ See *ibid.*, 258.

²⁴ See *ibid.*, 258.

²⁵ Only the possessions of the monastery in Gunzwil (1211, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 2), Hauptikon (1226, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 10), Herembrettyrchon (1226, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 10), Rossau (1226, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 10), Sparren (1226, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 9), Uerzlikon (1211, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 2; 1226, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 9), Winon (1211, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 2), Zurich (1226, Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 9, 11); see also Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 253

farmsteads, and were entitled to various types of taxes and duties²⁶. In addition, the monastery enjoyed various ecclesiastical rights in the communities of Rifferswil²⁷, Neuheim²⁸, Wiprechtswil (today Niederwil), Merenschwand²⁹, Baar³⁰, Beinwil im Freiamt³¹, Kilchberg with Wollishofen and Rüsclikon³², and, of course, in its immediate vicinity, such as in Hausen am Albis³³. The female Cistercian convents of Tänikon and Frauenthal were cared for spiritually from Kappel and also visited by the abbot of Kappel³⁴. The monastery church had a number of indulgences that brought pilgrims to Kappel on certain days³⁵; several lay brotherhoods had their centre at an altar in the monastery church³⁶.

From the beginning, the new abbot took a different approach than his predecessors. While the monastery had been embroiled in a whole series of lawsuits under his predecessors, Abbot Wolfgang seems to have rarely resorted to legal action³⁷. He apparently preferred to amicably settle legal claims that could no longer be enforced – for example, against the city of Zug, which had repeatedly interfered with the monastery’s authority in villages in the Zug area³⁸. Wolfgang’s interests seem to have lain in other areas: He continued a tradition that was in accordance with the rules of the order, but which had not been a particular focus at Kappel until then – the cultivation of learning. Until then, Kappel had not sent any members of the convent to study³⁹, and no writings by monks at Kappel are known⁴⁰. Abbot

²⁶ Otto Paul Clavadetscher provides a good overview in his *Beiträge zur Geschichte der Zisterzienserabtei Kappel am Albis*, Zurich 1946, 138–156.

²⁷ Incorporation in 1382: Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 135; see the informative process of 1406 (Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 167). Abbot Wolfgang Joner also presented a clergyman for the St. Nicolai chaplaincy to the Bishop of Constance here in 1522, namely Bartholomeus Stickel from Egenhausen (see Hundsnuerscher, *Investiturprotokolle*, 40).

²⁸ Incorporation in 1400: Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 155.

²⁹ Incorporation in 1398: *ibid.*, no. 148; see the informative process of 1406 (*ibid.*, no. 167) and the aforementioned regulation concerning vicars from 1400 (*ibid.*, no. 155).

³⁰ Incorporation 1255: *ibid.*, no. 73; see the informative process of 1406 (*ibid.*, no. 167) and the regulation concerning vicars from 1400 (*ibid.*, no. 155).

³¹ See the informative process of 1406 (*ibid.*, no. 167) and the aforementioned regulation concerning vicars of 1400 (*ibid.*, no. 155).

³² Incorporation 1408: *ibid.*, no. 168

³³ See Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 253.

³⁴ See *ibid.*, 246.

³⁵ See *ibid.*, 260, with notes 115 and 116.

³⁶ See *ibid.*, note 116. Mention is made of a plague brotherhood in honour of the martyr Sebastian (6 August 1492) and a St. John’s brotherhood (1415).

³⁷ See *ibid.*, 288. An overview of the monastery’s disputes since the Old Zurich War is provided by Clavadetscher, *Beiträge*, 111–113.

³⁸ See Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 288.

³⁹ See *ibid.*, 206.

⁴⁰ A certain exception is Abbot Guido/Wido at the beginning of the 13th century; see Salomon Vögelin, *Geschichte des Klosters Kappel im Kanton Zürich*, in *MAGZ* 3, 1845, 2; but even Vögelin sees a new approach

Wolfgang, on the other hand, made a name for himself quite early on as a promoter of scholarship: after serving as abbot for the first time at the end of 1520⁴¹, he was already appearing as a supporter of humanistic studies at the beginning of 1521. Zwingli, who had taken office in Zurich in the same year as Wolfgang Joner in Kappel, reported to his humanist correspondent Beatus Rhenanus on 8 April 1521:

Our Leo has translated the ‘Querela Pacis’ into German, which was sent to you by the abbot of Kappel Abbey to be printed⁴².

« Our Leo » is Leo Jud, who succeeded Zwingli as parish priest in Einsiedeln in 1519 and would become pastor at St. Peter’s in Zurich in 1523 – and the *Querela Pacis*, the « Complaint of Peace », is a widely read, impassioned plea penned by the famous humanist Erasmus of Rotterdam, calling for an end to the numerous wars that were ravaging Europe; a text that, although already politically outdated due to the renewed division between the Habsburgs and France when Erasmus published it in Latin in 1517, was nevertheless of particular interest in the Swiss Confederation, where the negative effects of mercenary service on the economy and society were becoming increasingly apparent. Incidentally, Zwingli was mistaken in thinking that Jud’s translation of Erasmus’s work had been published in Basel: in fact, *Klag des Frydens* appeared in 1521 at Froschauer in Zurich as one of the very first prints from this printing house.⁴³ However, Zwingli’s reference to the role played by Abbot Wolfgang Joner is correct. In his preface, Leo Jud not only explained that he had taken some liberties with Erasmus’ text,⁴⁴ but also described his motivation for producing the translation:

Nowadays, the whole world is inclined towards turmoil and war, and there are few who love and protect peace, hence great harm and evil, great destruction and forgetfulness befalls the Christian blood, everywhere people are robbed of

in Abbot Wolfgang’s policy: “Unlike his predecessors, his focus was not on accumulating monastery property, but on enlightening his conventuals” (Vögelin, *Geschichte*, 7).

⁴¹ See Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 287.

⁴² *Zwingli to Beatus Rhenanus*, 8 April 1521, in *Z VII*, Leipzig 1911, 439 [no. 173]: “Caetera Leo noster ‘Querelam pacis’ in linguam Germanicam traduxit, quae per abbatem monasterii Capellensis ad vos transmissa est, ut typis excudatur”.

⁴³ For the printing history, see Irmgard Bezzel, *Leo Jud (1482–1542) als Erasmusübersetzer. Ein Beitrag zur Erasmusrezeption im deutschsprachigen Raum*, in *DVJLG* 49, 1975, 628–644, here 632, note 26.

⁴⁴ This seems to have been done primarily with regard to the role of France: “But I must apologise for not praising the kingdom of France in German as highly as it is praised in Latin: Erasmus did this many years ago, and I have no doubt that he did so with good intentions for the country of France. But I have now changed my mind in those times, in those countries, where it seems to me that it is not necessary to praise France, as there are some who are inclined to love it for their own benefit rather than for the common good, which is why I thought it good to omit it” (Leo Jud, *Ein Klag des Frydens, der in allen Nationen und Landen verworfen, vertriben und erlegt*, Zurich 1521 [VD 16 E 3509], A1v). For Leo Jud’s profile as a translator specifically of Erasmus’ texts, see Bezzel, *Leo Jud*, 633.

their property, many widows and orphans are created, which is painful and pitiful to hear, let alone to see and suffer, especially among those who call themselves Christians after the one who is called (and indeed is) a prince of peace, *I have been moved to please and at the request of the venerable Lord Abbot of Kappel*, to translate into German a little book by the highly learned Erasmus of Rotterdam, which he wrote in Latin, from which (I hope) many may be improved and inspired to joy⁴⁵.

The fact that the abbot of Kappel encouraged the parish priest of Einsiedeln to translate a politically highly relevant work by Erasmus fits in with the image of a monastic superior who cared deeply about scholarship, as Heinrich Bullinger later described him. According to Bullinger, the abbot was

a God-fearing, learned, intelligent man, inclined towards the poor, who has had a great talent for preaching, teaching and learning, who himself preached often and fluently, and put all his mind into promoting and bringing forth the right teachings⁴⁶.

In fact, the appointment of the young Bullinger, who had just returned to Bremgarten in Aargau from his studies in Cologne as a newly qualified master, as a teacher at the monastery in Kappel can initially be understood entirely in this vein as part of Abbot Wolfgang's efforts to make his abbey a place of education and scholarship in best monastic tradition, drawing on the new impulses of humanism to achieve this. Given his interest in Erasmus' writings, it is not surprising that his choice for a teacher who was to instruct not only the monks themselves but also boys from the surrounding area as far away as Zurich, fell on a young humanist – and the curriculum that Abbot Wolfgang agreed with Bullinger was designed accordingly:

This schoolmaster Bullinger had to lecture from the Holy Scriptures for an hour every day, except Sundays, before noon. The abbot himself attended this lesson, together with the entire convent, and also allowed everyone free access. But before the schoolmaster began reading the Gospel of Matthew, he first read as much of *Erasmus' compendium theologiae* as he could. After noon, he had four hours in which he taught grammar and dialectics, alongside the authors *Cicero*, *Virgil*, *Sallust*, and the like. He also had his students copiously exercise in the *style*⁴⁷.

⁴⁵ Jud, *Ein Klag des Frydens*, A1v, (emphasis added by T. J.).

⁴⁶ Heinrich Bullinger, *Heinrich Bullingers Reformationsgeschichte, nach dem Autographon*, ed. by Johann J. Hottinger and Hans H. Vögeli, Frauenfeld 1838, here vol. 1, 91.

⁴⁷ Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 92. See also the account in the *Diarium*. "Praelegi in prophanis adolescentibus Donati rudimenta, constructiones Erasmi, Catonis disticha, Colloquia familiaria et Copiam verborum Erasmi, et quaedam Vergilii libros Aeneid. In sacris communiter omnibus monachis exponebam Paraclesim et compendium theologiae Erasmi, Locos communes Philippi, et evangelium

Both the great emphasis on style exercises and the choice of reading material were in keeping with a humanistic educational programme, and Bullinger's decision to make Erasmus himself a subject of instruction demonstrated this orientation unmistakably.

With the appointment of Bullinger, Abbot Wolfgang thus set the tone at the beginning of 1523 – although it must be acknowledged that his predecessors, despite having different priorities, had nevertheless provided a good basic foundation. A list compiled by Abbot Ulrich Trinkler in 1504 suggests that, after the monastery fire, a considerable amount of money had been invested in building up a good library, both for the monastery itself and for the Kappelerhaus in Zurich⁴⁸. And in a letter to Bullinger dated 21 December 1523, the pastor of Cham also raved about the opportunities for work in Kappel:

There is truly no one else who has so many volumes by the best writers at their disposal with which you can also train your talent [...] ⁴⁹.

In 1526, Abbot Wolfgang was still keen to expand the monastery library, for example when he urgently requested Joachim Vadian in St. Gallen to send his interpretation of the Acts of the Apostles to Kappel⁵⁰. Looking at the networks of the humanist-influenced Swiss reformers, it becomes clear that Abbot Wolfgang was in correspondence with Zwingli, Bullinger and Vadian, and especially in the late 1520s,

Matthaei ac Ioannis. In illud usi sumus interpretibus Erasmo, Melancht., Hieronymo et Chrysostomo, in hoc Erasmo, Melancht., Augustino, Cyrillo et Chrysostomo. Stylum supra modum exercitabam” (Heinrich Bullinger, *Diarium [Annales vitae] der Jahre 1504–1574*, e. by Emil Egli, Basel 1904 [QSRG 2], 7). On Bullinger's teaching activities in Kappel, see in particular Susi Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung zwischen Humanismus und Reformation. Eine Studie zu Heinrich Bullingers Römerbriefvorlesung von 1525*, Zurich 1970 (StDTh 27), 11–26, and Hans-Georg vom Berg, *Einleitung*, in *Heinrich Bullinger. Exegetische Schriften aus den Jahren 1525–1527*, Hans-Georg vom Berg and Susanna Hausammann (eds.), Zurich 1983 (*Heinrich Bullinger Werke, Dritte Abteilung: Theologische Schriften [HBTJS]* 1), 8–11, here 8; previously Fritz Blanke, *Der junge Bullinger 1504–1531*, Zurich 1942, 61–65, 67–70, and now Fritz Büsser, *Heinrich Bullinger (1504–1575). Leben, Werk und Wirkung*, vol. 1, Zurich 2004, 27–32.

⁴⁸ See Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 260, with note 122.

⁴⁹ *Jost Müller to Bullinger*, 21 December 1526, in *HBBW*, vol. 20, Zurich 2022, 733, 5 [no. 0 (sic)]: “Est profecto nihil cui in promptu sint tot volumina a summis autoribus aedita, quibus et tuum exercites ingenium”.

⁵⁰ See *Joner to Vadian*, 4 January 1526, in *Die Vadianische Briefsammlung der Stadtbibliothek St. Gallen*, ed. by Emil Arbenz [VBS], vol. 4: 1526–1530, St. Gallen, 1902 (*MVG* 28), 1 [no. 439]. See also *Bullinger to the Council and Citizens of Frankfurt am Main*, 25 August 1533 [dedication letter to his own interpretation of Acts], in *HBBW*, vol. 3, Zurich, 1983, 173–177 [no. 255].

Bullinger occasionally conveyed greetings from others to him⁵¹, but according to currently available sources, he was not a particularly prolific letter writer like Bullinger, and moved in humanist circles much less frequently than Vadian. Nevertheless, he fitted in well with the education-oriented milieu of the Swiss Reformers, as demonstrated by his measures to promote scholarship in Kappel and his request to Jud to translate Erasmus' text.

However, apart from the establishment of the school, the economic situation of Kappel Monastery, which had been problematic for some time, does not seem to have improved under Abbot Wolfgang. Time and again, the abbot and the convent had to certify that they were in debt; while the Zurich Council confiscated the treasures of all other monasteries within its sphere of influence since 1524 and kept them in central storage, Kappel was allowed to sell chasubles and other liturgical equipment in 1527 in order to pay off its debts⁵². The turn to the Reformation in fact meant a further deterioration in economic terms, because catholic donor families now began to reclaim their money from the monastery, as the purpose of their foundation, to read masses for the deceased, was no longer being fulfilled⁵³. The monastery's possessions outside Zurich's sphere of influence were seized by catholic rulers⁵⁴, and the abbot and convent at Kappel repeatedly experienced the legitimacy problems that the Reformation posed for dues owed to ecclesiastical institutions in disputes with their own peasants⁵⁵. It is therefore at least plausible that the complete transfer of the monastery and its estates to the Council of Zurich in the first half of 1527⁵⁶ was primarily motivated by economic reasons⁵⁷ – especially since the abbot and convent

⁵¹ For example, *Ambrosius Blarer to Bullinger*, 1 September 1528, in *HBBW*, vol. 1, 189, 9 [no. 30], *Johannes Oekolampad to Bullinger*, 4 October 1530, *ibid.*, 199, 4 [no. 36], or *Ulrich Stoll to Bullinger*, 30 June 1531, *ibid.*, 204, 6 [no. 38].

⁵² See Bullinger, *Reformationgeschichte*, vol. 1, 383.

⁵³ See, for example, the dispute with the Lords of Hallwil, who had long been associated with the monastery: *Die Regesten der ehemaligen Cistercienser-Abtei Cappel im Canton Zürich*, ed. by Gerold Ludwig Meyer von Kronau, Chur 1850, 31 [no. 368]; see also Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261.

⁵⁴ See, for example, the negative decision by Zug to Zurich, 20 August 1528, concerning the surrender of Kappel's possessions in the territories of the Junker von Hertenstein, in *Actensammlung zur Schweizerischen Reformationgeschichte in den Jahren 1521–1532, im Anschluss an die gleichzeitigen eidgenössischen Abschiede*, ed. by Johann Strickler, Zurich 1878–1884 [ASchweizerRef], vol. 1, 652 [no. 2075].

⁵⁵ See Emil Egli, *Die Reformation im Bezirke Affoltern*, in *Zürcher Taschenbuch* 11, 1888, 65–113, here 94.

⁵⁶ For dating, see Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 18, note 37 (terminus post quem is 25 February 1527, as Joner's wife is already mentioned), and Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261, with note 128 (terminus ante quem is 11 June 1527). The 1527 transfer memorandum can be found in the Zurich State Archives, C II.4, no. 609; an excerpt from the text is provided by Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 19, note 42.

⁵⁷ See also Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 18–20, contra Clavedetscher, *Beiträge*, 122.

had already had to accept supervision of their economic activities by Zurich since 1473⁵⁸.

Since the beginning of the Reformation, the exposed location of Kappel Monastery had meant that it was particularly close to the opponents of the Zurich Reformation. Sources repeatedly mention that threats and abusive speeches were made against the abbot and monastery of Kappel in Baar, Zug and Lucerne⁵⁹. The introduction of the Reformation in Kappel Abbey was accompanied by the loss of spiritual and secular rights in the Zug area⁶⁰, but at the same time, the church in Kappel was an important point of reference for those in Zug and beyond in Central Switzerland who were sympathetic to the Reformation⁶¹. Sources clearly show that Abbot Wolfgang and Bullinger made intensive efforts to support the forces of the Reformation in Zug in particular. In October 1529, Abbot Wolfgang admonished Zwingli and the Zurich Council to continue to work consistently for the approval of Protestant preaching in Zug, Schwyz and Uri.

Therefore, I hereby demonstrate with this brief and concise writing how I am still being challenged in many ways by devout Christian people from the three cantons of Zug, Schwyz and Uri, who undoubtedly cherish God's word and righteousness and who await salvation. That I, to the best of my ability, am obliged to my lords and benefactors, since God has brought them to such renown, to command all strength and courage, [that] we may now use all means to the glory of God and the protection of the oppressed. [...] And all that has been communicated to me, not only verbally but also in writing, I have not wanted to withhold from you, in strict confidence towards my gracious lords, so that you may bring the matter to a conclusion with greater steadfastness⁶².

However, this geographical proximity to the five inner Swiss cantons also posed a real military threat to Kappel, which was noted with great concern and reported to Zurich. The monastery's many contacts in the Zug area opened up channels for espionage activities, and indeed, Abbot Wolfgang's reports on intelligence findings from Central Switzerland increasingly dominate the source

⁵⁸ See Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 247 and 258.

⁵⁹ See Clavadetscher, *Kappel*, 106–110.

⁶⁰ See e.g. *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 1, 722 [no. 934b] (interrogation transcript, Zurich, November 1524); 712 [no. 2228] (intelligence report, 1528); 652 [no. 2075] (Zug to Zurich, 20 August 1528); *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 3, 215 [no. 492] (Berger to Zurich, 27 April 1531); 239 [no. 550] (Zug to Zurich, 8 May 1531).

⁶¹ For more details, see Joachim Staedtke, *Heinrich Bullingers Bemühungen um eine Reformation im Kanton Zug*, in *Zwingliana* 10, 1954, 24–47.

⁶² *Joner to Zwingli*, 6 October 1529, in Z X, 315 [no. 924], also in *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 2, 334 [no. 866].

material from 1529 onwards⁶³. Abbot Wolfgang and the bailiff Heinrich Peyer von Knonau also immediately reported to Zurich the actual departure of the catholic troops for the Second War of Kappel on 4 October 1531. The military catastrophe that subsequently forced Zurich and the other members of the *Burgrecht* to conclude the Second Peace of Kappel was certainly not due to a lack of knowledge about the enemy's activities⁶⁴. Abbot Wolfgang died, as did Zwingli, on 11 October 1531 in the Battle of Kappel, which was followed by the plundering of his monastery⁶⁵.

2. A practitioner of the Reformation

When, on 25 February 1527, he led the Zurich widow Grimm to the Fraumünster for their wedding⁶⁶, and shortly afterwards, together with his convent, handed over the Kappel monastery to the Zurich Council, Wolfgang Joner demonstrated his final departure from the customs of the medieval church: celibacy and the inviolability of ecclesiastical foundations were central pillars of an ecclesiastical legal system that had developed since the early Middle Ages. However, his departure from these ideas came as no surprise at this point, as Abbot Wolfgang

⁶³ The Zurich councillors were well aware of Kappel's potential, as evidenced by their request to Abbot Wolfgang Joner in 1527 to make enquiries about a possible alliance between Central Switzerland and Austria (*ASchweizerRef*, vol. 1, 553 [no. 1764], *Zurich to Joner*, 22 July 1527); similar requests for reconnaissance activities were made in early 1529 (*ibid.*, vol. 2, 49 [no. 105], *Zurich to Joner*, 18 February 1529); see also the role assigned to Kappel in the war plans of June 1531 (*ibid.*, vol. 3, 279 [no. 648]) and the request for increased reconnaissance activities dated 23 September 1531 (*ibid.*, 573 [no. 1409]). The reports from Kappel compiled by Strickler alone show how extensive the information about Central Switzerland was that Zurich had at its disposal from this source: *ibid.*, vol. 2, 86 [no. 179] (*Joner to Zurich*, 13 March 1529); 174 [no. 423] (*Joner to Zurich*, 2 June 1529); 296 [no. 786] (*Joner to Zurich*, 4 September 1529); *ibid.*, vol. 3, 60 [no. 154] (*Joner to Zurich*, 15 February 1531); 122 [no. 264] (*Joner to Simler*, 20/27 March 1531); no. 338, 149 (*Joner to Zurich*, 1 April 1531); no. 492, 215 (*Hans Berger to Zurich*, 27 April 1531); 301 [no. 693] (*Joner to Mayor Röst*, 6 June 1531); 334 [no. 780] (*Heinrich Peyer of Knonau to Zurich*, 24 June 1531); no. 827, 350 (*Joner to Zurich*, 30 June 1531); 380 [no. 883] (*Berger and Peyer to Zurich*, 3 July 1531); 414 [no. 974] (*Joner to Zurich*, 16 July 1531); 434 [no. 1031] (*Joner to Zurich*, 26 July 1531); 448 [no. 1072] (*Zurich to Kappel and Bremgarten*, 1 August 1531); 543 [no. 1332] (*Berger and Peyer to Zurich*, 12 September 1531); 545 [no. 1336] and 547 [no. 1343] (*Berger and Peyer to Zurich*, 13 September 1531 and reply from the same day); 580 [no. 1431a] (*Joner and Peyer to Zurich*, 27 September 1531); 582 [no. 1440] (*Joner to Zurich*, 28 September 1531); 586 [no. 1473] (*Joner and Peyer to Zurich*, 3 October 1531); 614 [no. 1522] (*Joner and Peyer to Zurich*, 4 October 1531).

⁶⁴ See Egli, *Reformation*, 111.

⁶⁵ *Christian Fribolt to Vadian*, 13 October 1531, in *VBS*, vol. 5, 22 [no. 649]; *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 4, 32 [no. 102]; Bullinger, *Diarium*, 20; 127; *Bullinger to Martin Bucer*, 6 October 1537, in *HBBW*, vol. 7, 282–295 [no. 1053], with note 53 on the handling of the abbot's corpse; see also Locher, *Reformation*, 534; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 289.

⁶⁶ Bullinger, *Diarium*, 10,21; Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 109; see *HBBW*, vol. 1, 48, note 4; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 288; Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 17.

had long since made a name for himself as a representative of the Reformation in the Zurich countryside; in 1888, Emil Egli even characterised him as « one of the most important proponents of the Zurich Reformation⁶⁷ ». It is now worth taking a closer look at this profile as a practitioner of the Reformation.

2.1 First signs of a reformist attitude

The preserved sources provide only vague indications as to how exactly the Lord Abbot of Kappel came to be open to the Reformation. The Latin letter sent in November 1523 under Abbot Wolfgang's name to Rudolf Asper, parish priest in Oberrüti in Aargau⁶⁸, already shows clear signs of stylisation that would be more appropriate to an advanced stage of development than to the early stages. It has been preserved in a copy written by Bullinger, who noted under his copy that he himself had « extemporised » this letter « in the name of the abbot⁶⁹ ». However, the text is carefully crafted, from the rhetorically skilful exordium, which barely conceals an extensive knowledge of classical antiquity⁷⁰, to the argumentation with its numerous quotations from Church Fathers and scholastic authors, to the signs of a reception of Reformation writings from the Wittenberg context⁷¹, to such an extent that the « ex tempore » in the addendum to Bullinger's copy should rather be understood as a case of the *humilitas* motif.

As this document claims, Abbot Wolfgang, who is listed as the sender⁷² and who, alienated from Asper because of his devotion to the Reformation's scriptural

⁶⁷ Egli, *Reformation*, 72.

⁶⁸ For identification, see Willy Brändli, *Ein Brief Bullingers an einen bisher unbekanntem Adressaten*, in *Zwingliana* 8/10, 1948, 601–603. On Asper, see also Manfred Krebs, *Die Annatenregister des Bistums Konstanz aus dem 15. Jahrhundert*, in *FD A* 76, 1956, 216 [no. 2305]. Asper died before May 1525, as his benefice was then filled by a new incumbent; see Hundsnurscher, *Investiturprotokolle*, 671.

⁶⁹ Heinrich Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, ed. by Bernhard Schneider, in *HBTS*, vol. 2, 19–31, here 31, note g: “Hanc epistolam scripsimus abbatis nomine, ex tempore”. A regest is provided in *HBBW*, vol. 1, 257 [Appendix 2, no. 1]. An analysis of the content is provided by Susi Hausammann, *Anfragen zum Schriftverständnis des jungen Bullinger im Zusammenhang einer Interpretation von De scripturae negotio*, in *Heinrich Bullinger 1504–1575, Gesammelte Aufsätze zum 400. Todestag*, ed. by Ulrich Gäbler and Erland Herkenrath, Zurich 1975, vol. 1, 29–48.

⁷⁰ Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 21.

⁷¹ See the frequent references to Martin Luther's writings in the apparatus to Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 21–31; on these, see also Hausammann, *Anfragen*. This could be corroborated by a comparison with Philipp Melancthon's writings known to Bullinger; there are clear echoes, in particular, of the *Epistola dedicatoria* and the introduction to the *Loci Communes* of 1521; see Philipp Melancthon, *Loci communes rerum theologicarum seu hypotyposes theologicae*, 1521, in *Melancthon's Werke*, vol. 2/1, Hans Engelland and Robert Stupperich (ed.), Gütersloh 1978, 16–21; 28.

⁷² “Egregio viro Rodolpho Aspero, amico syncerissimo Volcatius. S.D” (Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 21). See also the concluding indication of the place of composition: “Ex coenobio nostro Cappell” (Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 31) – although Bullinger was certainly also in Kappel at the time in

principle, attempts to persuade him to resume their former *amicitia*, had become weary of the contradictory canonical texts on the detour (described as a gradual ascent⁷³) via the Church Fathers to the study of scripture⁷⁴. The exhortations of the Fathers themselves appear to have been decisive in this regard: in the writings of Cyprian of Carthage⁷⁵, Augustine⁷⁶, Jerome⁷⁷, but also Hilary of Portiers⁷⁸, Jean Gerson⁷⁹, and, incidentally, also in the writings of John Chrysostom, Cyril of Alexandria, Gregory of Nazianzus, Athanasius of Alexandria, Origen, Ambrose of Milan and Tertullian⁸⁰, there are clear references to Holy Scripture being the decisive authority in theological matters⁸¹. Referring to a (probably apocryphal) quotation from the Cistercian Saint Bernard of Clairvaux, the study of Scripture is praised as « drinking from the springs themselves rather than from the rivulets⁸² », and is described on the basis of a series of passages from the Old and New Testaments as a delightful experience of being addressed by Christ himself⁸³, who, after all, repeatedly made it clear « that he wants to be recognised from the Scriptures alone⁸⁴ ». The New Testament is « nothing other than the interpretation of the Old⁸⁵ » and the Epistle to the Romans contains instructions for understanding the entire Holy Scripture⁸⁶. The Epistle to the Romans also refutes the argument opposed to the principle of Scripture that not all theologically relevant facts can be found in the Bible⁸⁷. Anyone who reads the Church Fathers carefully will notice that the canonical writings were not approved, but rather

question, the first-person plural possessive pronoun is more in keeping with the conventions of official correspondence, as befits an office.

⁷³ “quod laboribus tam facile superatis (per patres) veluti per gradus quospiam in rerum summam transcenderam” (Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 27); Bullinger noted “anacephaleosis” in the margin of his copy of the letter (*ibid.*, note G).

⁷⁴ Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 22; see Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 31.

⁷⁵ See Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 22.

⁷⁶ See *ibid.*, 23. The fact that one of the passages from Augustine is quoted with reference to the *Decretum Gratiani* suggests that the previous statements about canon law studies were at least more than a mere reiteration of the usual humanist polemic.

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*, 24.

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*

⁷⁹ *Ibid.*

⁸⁰ *Ibid.* Unlike the aforementioned ecclesiastical writers, here there is only a summary reference and no specific citation of individual passages.

⁸¹ See *ibid.*, 26.

⁸² *Ibid.*, 24: “Quanto vero melius, iuxta Bernardi nostri vocem ex fontibus ipsis bibere quam ex rivulis?” See also *ibid.*, note 42, which suggests that Bullinger here quoted Martin Luther from his *Assertio omnium articulorum*, printed in 1520; see Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 33.

⁸³ Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 4; see Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 35.

⁸⁴ Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 25: “ex solis scripturis cognosci vult”.

⁸⁵ *Ibid.*, 25: “invenio novum testamentum aliud non esse quam veteris interpretationem”; see Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 35–37, 39.

⁸⁶ See Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 25.

⁸⁷ See *ibid.*, 25.

received by the Church, which is why their reliability and sufficiency cannot be doubted⁸⁸. Since even the Early Church did not yet have access to the writings of the Church Fathers or the medieval scholastics, one must rather assume, with Augustine (and in accordance with a whole series of relevant Bible passages⁸⁹), that Scripture itself provides sufficient material for its own understanding⁹⁰, especially since the Church Fathers themselves, when they disagreed, referred back to Scripture⁹¹. This in no way implies a disregard for the Church Fathers and later theologians, but rather follows their example and takes seriously the fact that we ourselves read the same Holy Scriptures that they studied⁹². The councils, on the other hand, had often erred⁹³, and numerous undesirable developments had clearly arisen from the custom that was also regarded as authoritative⁹⁴. Thus, the shift from traditional decrees to the study of Scripture was not what the opponents of the Reformation thought it was:

For the time being, you have me as someone who does not want to rest in flesh and blood, who does not want to sow heresy, that is, sects, who does not want to introduce new teachings, but rather who believes in the Spirit, seeks harmony, [and] revives the old, evangelical and apostolic teaching⁹⁵.

Why Wolfgang Joner commissioned his schoolmaster Bullinger to write this letter is not clear from the sources⁹⁶. However, since the letter was sent to Asper in his name, it can be assumed that the abbot had adopted Bullinger's wording as his own. In addition, it apparently provoked a negative response from Asper⁹⁷, and was therefore probably also regarded by him as an expression of Joner's opinion. At the end of 1523, it was therefore in Wolfgang Joner's interest to present himself to third parties as a staunch supporter of the *sola scriptura* principle.

Two observations reinforce the impression that in 1523 the Lord of Kappel was no longer at the beginning of the path to the Reformation but had already come

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*, 26; see Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 36–41.

⁸⁹ See Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 28.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*, 27; see Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 41.

⁹¹ Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 27.

⁹² See *ibid.*, 29.

⁹³ *Ibid.*, 29; see Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 47.

⁹⁴ Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 30. It is not entirely clear whether the term “consuetudo” refers here to the *consuetudines* belonging to the normative structure of the Cistercian Order or whether it refers more generally to customs that have become common practice.

⁹⁵ *Ibid.*, 30: “Tu interim habes me nolle carni et sanguini acquiescere, nolle haereses, hoc est sextas, seminare, nolle novas doctrinas introducere, sed spiritui me credere, concordiae studere, veterem doctrinam evangelicam et apostolicam revocare”.

⁹⁶ See Bernhard Schneider, *Introduction to De scripturae negotio*, in *HBTS*, vol. 2, 19; Brändli, *Letter*, 602; Vögelin, *Wolfgang Joner*, 5; Hausammann, *Anfragen*, 30.

⁹⁷ At least, that is what Bullinger himself noted under his copy of the letter: “At Rodolphus eam sic consuluit, ut nesciam an ingrator fuerit an impatientior” (Bullinger, *De scripturae negotio*, 31, note G).

a long way along it. These observations concern, on the one hand, the terms of employment he granted Bullinger in Kappel and, on the other hand, Abbot Wolfgang's actions at the First Zurich Disputation.

In his memoirs, Bullinger attaches great importance to the fact that the abbot allowed him to not attend convent mass and divine office, and also exempted him from other monastic obligations:

My religion remained intact, and I had nothing to do with monastic vows, monasticism, the habit, singing, divine office, the church and papal superstition, which were still flourishing at that time. During this time, however, I increasingly distanced myself from superstition and turned towards the true religion and was not forced to participate in any sacred ceremonies. I did go to church, however, and prayed to God in a secluded place; I also listened to the sacred sermons⁹⁸.

Bullinger's appointment in Kappel was followed by a very productive period: During this time, he was introduced to the circle of Zurich reformers, was able to put his own ideas about a humanistic theological education into practice for the first time, gained experience as a lecturer and preacher, wrote his first major and minor works, and began to publish⁹⁹. If his later reflections on this period are to be believed, this also had to do with the freedom and support granted to him by his employer. Bullinger therefore referred to Wolfgang Joner as his «patron¹⁰⁰» and dedicated several writings to him¹⁰¹. He sometimes referred to the abbot when contacting others¹⁰². Research suggests that he consulted with Abbot Wolfgang before writing

⁹⁸ Bullinger, *Diarium*, 8,3–9: “religio mihi manebat integra, nec quicquam mihi erat negotii cum votis monasticis, cum monachatu, cuculla, cantu, choro, templo et cum superstitione papistica, quae tum plane florebat. Ego vero in dies magis atque magis ab straherbar a superstitione ad veram religionem, neque vero cogebam ullis interesse sacris. Ingrediebar tamen templum et in abdito aliquo loco precabar Dominum. Audiebam item conciones sacras”; see Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 91. On Bullinger's terms of employment in Kappel, see also Blanke, *Der junge Bullinger*, 56–59.

⁹⁹ See Endre Zsindely and Ulrich Gäbler, *Introduction*, in *HBBW*, vol. 1, 23–28, here 24, as well as Büsser, *Bullinger*, vol. 1, 50–59.

¹⁰⁰ “Maecenas”: for example, Bullinger, *Diarium*, 12; 127; in his letter of dedication to the Council of Frankfurt am Main accompanying his commentary on the Acts of the Apostles, Bullinger refers to Joner in 1535 as “meconati meo omniumque studiosorum patrono d. Wolphgango Ionero” (25 August 1535, in *HBBW*, vol. 3, 175 [no. 255]).

¹⁰¹ *HBBW*, vol. 1, 53 [no. 3] (dedicatory preface to the treatise on providence, October/November 1524); 79 [no. 10] (dedicatory preface to *De Propheta*, 31 August 1525); 119 [no. 20] (*Bullinger to Joner*, May/June 1526); *HBBW*, vol. 1, 259 [Appendix 2, no. 10] (Dedicatory preface to *De origine erroris in negotio Eucharistiae ac Missae*, 27 December 1527).

¹⁰² For example, *Bullinger to Rudolf Weingartner*, 15 October 1524, in *HBBW*, vol. 1, 48–52 [no. 2], here 48, 10–49, 5.

his marriage proposal to Anna Adlischwyler on 30 September 1527¹⁰³, but in any case, the Lord of Kappel was one of the few guests with whom Bullinger celebrated his wedding in August 1529¹⁰⁴, and when Bullinger's daughter Anna was born in 1530, Abbot Wolfgang acted as her godfather¹⁰⁵. Even when the abbot sent a messenger to Bremgarten on 3 October 1531 with important information about the impending attack by the catholic forces, he sent the man to Bullinger because he assumed that their mutual trust would lead Bullinger to take the warning more seriously than another recipient might have done¹⁰⁶.

In addition to the terms of employment of the young Bullinger, the abbot's behaviour at the First Zurich Disputation is revealing: at the very end, Erhard Hegenwald reports in his printed account of what happened in Zurich on 29 January 1523,

The honourable Mr N. etc., abbot of Cappel, also spoke: Where are those who want to burn us and bring wood? Why are they not stepping forward now¹⁰⁷?

Even if one takes into account that this report has been edited for literary purposes and does not constitute a transcript in the classical sense, the fact remains that the abbot of Kappel took a clear position in favour of Zwingli's reformatory programme at the First Zurich Disputation – even though at that time there was still serious opposition, both in the Grossmünster monastery itself and in other Zurich monasteries, and ultimately also in circles of the leading families. Abbot Wolfgang's position was therefore probably not opportunistic, but rather an expression of genuine agreement. This is consistent with Zwingli's statement to Nikolaus von Wattenwil in July 1523, in which he explicitly listed the Abbot of Kappel as one of the senior clergy who were positively disposed towards the Reformation¹⁰⁸.

2.2 Commitment to the Zurich Reformation

¹⁰³ *Bullinger to Anna Adlischwyler*, 30 September 1527, in *HBBW*, vol. 1, 126–141 [no. 24], here 132, note 134.

¹⁰⁴ Bullinger, *Diarium*, 18. The sermon was delivered by Peter Simler, Prior of Kappel.

¹⁰⁵ *Ibid.*, 19.

¹⁰⁶ See *Joner to Bullinger*, 3 October 1531, in *HBBW*, vol. 1, 217 [no. 40], also in *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 3, 594 [no. 1473].

¹⁰⁷ Proceedings of the assembly in the city of Zurich on 29 January 1523, in *Z I*, 479–569 [no. 18], here 568, 13–16.

¹⁰⁸ *Zwingli to Nikolaus von Wattenwil*, 31 July 1523, in *Z VIII*, 101–105 [no. 311], here 105: “Hoc quoque audi, quod non parvi momenti est, abbates, qui bene sentiunt, hi fere sunt, quos ego sciam: abbas sancti Urbani, abbas Capellae, administrator Eremiti, abbas Fabariensis; praepositi, quos primo loco ponere debui, tu et Imbriacensis soli estis ex omnibus, quos ego sciam, qui bene de doctrina Christi sentient”.

Abbot Wolfgang also sided with Zwingli in the Second Zurich Disputation at the end of October 1523: after Zwingli had explained his rejection of the sacrifice of the Mass in detail on the second day, 27 October 1523, Vadian, as president of the disputation, first asked the Abbot of Kappel for his opinion. The abbot stated that Zwingli's opinion « agrees well with me and is right¹⁰⁹ », an assessment immediately endorsed by the provost of Embrach, who reported that he agreed « in every respect with the abbot of Kappel¹¹⁰ ».

However, Abbot Wolfgang went beyond simply expressing his *agreement* with Zwingli's demands for reform – towards the end of the Second Disputation, he expressly urged the Zurich Council to resolutely promote the Reformation and offered his own *assistance*: according to the minutes, he declared that

he would spare no effort within his power but would gladly contribute with his own person; for there must be preaching if one wished to be called a true Christian¹¹¹.

The Zurich Council quickly accepted this proposal. Together with the three parish priests of the city, namely Zwingli from Grossmünster, Engelhardt from Fraumünster and Jud from St. Peter's, as well as four councillors, the abbot of Kappel, the commander of Küsnacht and the provost of Embrach were to form a commission tasked with guiding the clergy in the city and, above all, in the countryside towards the Reformation. The literary product of this commission is Zwingli's *Kurze christliche Einleitung* (*Short Christian Introduction*)¹¹², but also the division of the countryside into three districts, in which Commander Konrad Schmid of Küsnacht, Zwingli himself and Abbot Wolfgang were to travel from place to place as itinerant preachers and spread the teachings of the Reformation among the people. Abbot Wolfgang was assigned the countryside beyond the Albis¹¹³.

This was the first time that the Lord of Kappel had assumed the role that he would repeatedly perform in the following period for the slowly emerging Reformed Church of Zurich: that of a kind of spiritual councillor. Again and again in the 1520s, the Zurich Council set up commissions to either carry out executive tasks – such as the preaching tours through the countryside in 1523 and 1524, of which we

¹⁰⁹ *Records of the second disputation* from 26 to 28 October 1523, in Z II, 671–803 [no. 28], here 734.

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 737.

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*, 802.

¹¹² Huldrych Zwingli, *A Brief Christian Introduction*, in Z II, 628–663 [no. 27].

¹¹³ *Zwingli to Vadian*, 11 November 1523, in Z VIII, 129–131 [no. 321], also in *VBS*, vol. 3, 43 [no. 368].

unfortunately have very little evidence¹¹⁴ – or to examine controversial issues and draw up proposals for further action for the attention of the mayor and the Council.

These commissions regularly included a small number of councillors and leading clergymen: often the three parish priests of the city churches and the three clergymen frequently referred to by researchers as «country prelates», namely Brennwald, Schmid, and Joner. In the commission lists, Abbot Wolfgang is always named first among the prelates. One need not conclude, as Emil Egli did, that Abbot Wolfgang was to the countryside what Zwingli was to the city¹¹⁵ – but it is true that at a time when questions of protocol were anything but trivial, it was a special sign of prestige when Joner always figured as the first of the higher clergy – incidentally, this was also the case in 1528 at the first Zurich synod, where he headed the list of clergy of the Knonau district in the minutes¹¹⁶.

This was also the case when, on 10 December 1523, the Council decided to set up a commission to examine and draw up proposals on how to deal with the controversial celebration of the Mass¹¹⁷. The immediate cause were complaints from the provost of Grossmünster about chaplains who refused to read Mass and about those who did read Mass being insulted for doing so. When Konrad Grebel wrote a letter to Vadian expressing his strong disapproval of the fact that people like Abbot Wolfgang, of all people, had been sent to this commission, the councillor's son, who felt that the Reformation in Zurich was progressing far too slowly, showed himself to be not only opinionated¹¹⁸ but also well informed: Wolfgang Joner and the other two prelates once again agreed with Zwingli and the other city priests on *the substance of the matter*, but with regard to the specific *practical* approach, they submitted a dissenting opinion that deviated from the advice of the city priests, calling for restraint from hasty reform measures. Mass should not be banned, and disturbances of Mass services should be dealt with in the same way as insults to clergy who read Mass – but no one should be forced to read Mass against their conscience¹¹⁹. The Council agreed to this proposal; it was not until April 1525 that Mass was officially abolished in Zurich and

¹¹⁴ Egli offers some insights in *Reformation*, 89.

¹¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 72.

¹¹⁶ See Egli, *Actensammlung*, 601 [no. 1391]. Abbot Wolfgang is listed here in his capacity as rector of the parish of Hausen, but with the title of abbot (“Hausen: H. Abt von Cappel”).

¹¹⁷ *Ibid.*, 182 [no. 456].

¹¹⁸ See *Grebel to Vadian*, 18 December 1523, in *VBS*, vol. 3, 50: “Illi neglecta sententia divina de non missando medium praescriperunt prudentia (scio) diabolica. Illud cras referetur ad utrunque senatum, et sic missandum erit”.

¹¹⁹ *The other opinion of the Mass*, in *Z II*, 811–813 [no. 29/2].

replaced by the Reformed celebration of the Lord's Supper – and in between, in 1524, a commission consisting of the three provincial prelates and the three city pastors was again appointed to consider how to proceed with regard to images and Mass, whose vote, presented at the end of May 1524, now advocated reforms¹²⁰. These recommendations then led to the Zurich Council's mandate on images in June 1524 – which, however, was not implemented in Kappel until 9 March 1525¹²¹.

These observations show Abbot Wolfgang as a clergyman who, on the one hand, was thoroughly on Zwingli's side in terms of content and theology, but who, on the other hand, had a very keen eye for what was possible when and where, and who therefore preferred to proceed cautiously. What did not please Konrad Grebel appears, in view of what can be learned from sources in the immediate vicinity of Kappel Monastery, to have been an expression of strategic wisdom: in the summer of 1524, the Council of Zug imposed a fine on those who attended Abbot Wolfgang's sermons¹²², in November 1524, the Zurich Council received reports from Baar of blasphemous speeches and threats against the abbot and convent of Kappel¹²³, and in late summer 1525, even direct subjects of Kappel Monastery threatened to stop paying taxes if Mass were abolished in the monastery church¹²⁴. The latter was an unsuccessful attempt to halt the development: with the express support of the Zurich Council, Mass was no longer celebrated in Kappel from 4 September 1525 onwards¹²⁵.

According to Bullinger, Abbot Wolfgang waited until the end of March 1526 to introduce the Reformed Communion¹²⁶ – this also confirms the impression of a rather cautious approach, which seems all the more justified given that the abolition of Mass alone caused massive economic difficulties for the monastery: the von Hallwil family, who had long been associated with the Cistercian abbey of Kappel, demanded

¹²⁰ Egli, *Actensammlung*, 231 [no. 532] (Council decision of 16 May 1524); see Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 162; 164; *HBBW*, vol. 1, 48, note 4; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 288. The joint advice of parish priests and prelates can be found in Z III, 120–131 [no. 35]; see also Emil Egli, *Vorschlag wegen der Bilder und der Messe. Einleitung*, in Z III, 114–118, here 114.

¹²¹ Bullinger, *Diarium*, 10; see Z X, 314, note 1; *HBBW*, vol. 1, 24 and 48; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261; Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 16.

¹²² See Locher, *Reformation*, 423; Staedtke, *Kanton Zug*, 33.

¹²³ *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 1, 722 [no. 934b]; see Egli, *Reformation*, 77; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 288.

¹²⁴ Egli, *Actensammlung*, 338 [no. 814]; see Egli, *Reformation*, 93; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261; Kamber, *Reformation*, 346.

¹²⁵ See Z X, 314, note 1; *HBBW*, vol. 1, 48, note 4; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261; Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 17; Staedtke, *Kanton Zug*, 27.

¹²⁶ Bullinger, *Diarium*, 10; Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 92; see Z X, 314, note 1; *HBBW*, vol. 1, 24, 48, note 4; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261; Hausammann, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 17; Bernhard Schneider, *Einleitung zu De pane eucharistiae declamationes*, in *HBTS*, vol. 2, 108–110, here 109.

the return of their donated goods, interest and tithes from the monastery as early as the beginning of 1526 and with the support of the Lucerne authorities, because the abbot and the convent refused to fulfil the foundation's purpose due to the abolition of the Mass¹²⁷. The negotiations dragged on for almost the entire year, and at the beginning of December 1526, the abbot and the convent had to agree to an arbitration ruling, according to which they had to pay the von Hallwil family compensation for the Masses that had not been read¹²⁸.

Abbot Wolfgang's ability to navigate this challenging environment is also reflected in the fact that he was repeatedly appointed by the Zurich Council to sit in committees tasked with preparing sensitive matters: When, at the end of 1523, opposition within the Grossmünster chapter mounted its last significant resistance against Zwingli, the Council ruled that Abbot Wolfgang, together with the Commander of Küsnacht, the Provost of Embrach, the Provost of Grossmünster and two other Grossmünster canons, should take up the matter: Zwingli and the other two city pastors were to be confronted before the commission with Canon Konrad Hofmann and the other critics of the Reformation, and the outcome of this discussion was to be reported to the Council¹²⁹. The commission worked quickly: the discussion took place on 13 and 14 January 1524, and the commission's report to the Council is dated 19 January 1524 and testifies to a thoroughly energetic exchange of blows¹³⁰. Abbot Wolfgang, who was the first to sign the report, appears here as a member of a commission before which Zwingli and his two fellow pastors, Engelhardt and Leu, had to answer, at least officially, once again to the criticism of their catholic opponents.

Joner's name appears again alongside these three in August 1524, when the Council decreed that a commission consisting of council members, the three city pastors and the three rural prelates should interrogate Wilhelm Reublin. Originally a parish priest at St. Alban's in Basel, he had been dismissed from his post there for his reformist activities and had been given the parish of Witikon in 1522, where he soon

¹²⁷ *Regesten der Cistercienser-Abtei Cappel*, 31 [no. 368]; *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 1, 522 [no. 1635] (24 January 1526); see Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261 and 268. The von Hallwil family had long been associated with the abbey and held the castellan rights over Kappel until 1495; see Vögelin, *Kappel*, 11.

¹²⁸ *Regesten der Cistercienser-Abtei Cappel*, 31 [no. 369].

¹²⁹ Egli, *Actensammlung*, 190. [no. 465]; Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 139–142. For a summary of the events, with particular reference to Konrad Hofmann, see also Alfred Schindler, *Die Anliegen des Chorherrn Hofmann*, in *Zwingliana* 23, 1996, 63–82, here 80, as well as Josef Brülisauer, *Neue Beiträge zur Biographie Konrad Hofmanns*, in *Zwingliana* 23, 1996, 11–62, here 43–45.

¹³⁰ Egli, *Actensammlung*, 197–199 [no. 483]; see Locher, *Reformation*, 139.

attracted negative attention for his criticism of tithing and, above all, infant baptism, and was eventually arrested¹³¹.

The issue of infant baptism became more and more of a serious problem for the Zurich authorities¹³². After reports from the Grüningen district that the Anabaptists there claimed, among other things, that they had never been given a proper hearing in Zurich¹³³, the Council responded by scheduling another (the third) official Anabaptist disputation on 7 and 8 November 1525. In the presence of a delegation from the dignitaries of the Grüningen district, the leading Anabaptists were invited to debate with the Zurich priests around Zwingli. According to Bullinger, the occasion was chaired by Abbot Wolfgang, Commander Schmid of Küsnacht, the Schaffhausen preacher Sebastian Hoffmeister and the St. Gallen mayor Vadian¹³⁴. The huge public interest meant that the event had to be moved from the town hall to the Grossmünster; the fact that the presiding officers and the city pastors sat together at one table and the Anabaptists at another was however a clear indication of the unsurprising outcome:

After the discussion was over, Grebel, Mantz, Blaurock and other Anabaptist patriarchs were brought before the council and admonished to abandon their intentions, which had been publicly found to be wrong. However, as this had no effect on the stubborn heads, they were kept in prison. However, they were soon released again, with a serious warning that if they continued with their schism, they would be severely punished¹³⁵.

Regardless of the specific content of this dispute with the Anabaptists, it is of interest here that the Zurich Council once again turned to the Abbot of Kappel to advance the Reformation. On the one hand, they relied on his reputation, and on the other, they counted on his experience in dealing with delicate situations¹³⁶.

¹³¹ Establishment of the commission: Council decision of 11 August 1524, in Egli, *Actensammlung*, 246 [no. 567].

¹³² See, among many others, Andrea Strübind, *Eifriger als Zwingli*, 147–202; 293–470; C. Arnold Snyder, *Swiss Anabaptism. The Beginnings, 1523–1525*, in *A Companion to Anabaptism and Spiritualism 1521–1700*, ed. by John D. Roth and James M. Stayer, Leiden/Boston 2007, 45–48; Urs B. Leu, *Huldrych Zwingli und die Täufer*, in *Die Zürcher Täufer 1525–1700*, ed. by Urs B. Leu and Christian Scheidegger, Zurich 2007, 15–66; id., *Das Täuferium auf dem Zürcher Gebiet und in der Nordostschweiz* in *Kinder des Friedens. 500 Jahre Täuferium in der Schweiz*, ed. by Oliver Dürr et al., Zurich 2025, 17–79.

¹³³ For more on Anabaptist activities there and their connection to peasant unrest, see Strübind, *Eifriger als Zwingli*, 428–439, which critically examines the existing research literature.

¹³⁴ Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 294–298; see Leu, *Huldrych Zwingli und die Täufer*, 47.

¹³⁵ Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 298.

¹³⁶ See also *Konrad Grebel* [cousin of the Anabaptist of the same name] *to Vadian*, 20 March 1527, in *VBS*, vol. 4, 50 [no. 478], and *Joner to Vadian*, 16 May 1527, *VBS*, vol. 4, 59 [no. 485], on Joner's role in negotiations concerning tithes.

The abbot of Kappel was also originally intended to be part of the Zurich delegation to the Bern disputation in early 1528, but he was allowed to send a representative due to illness¹³⁷. The Council repaid him for his services by, among other things, dismissing a complaint in June 1527 from the community of Hausen, which would have preferred to have its own resident pastor rather than receiving spiritual care from the Kappel monastery. For the time being, the people of Hausen continued to receive their preachers and pastors from Kappel¹³⁸, including, from mid-1528, the Kappel schoolmaster Heinrich Bullinger¹³⁹.

2.3 The spread of the Reformation in Swiss Cistercian monasteries

An important part of Abbot Wolfgang's work as a practitioner of the Reformation was therefore his participation in council commissions. Time and again, when important concrete decisions on church reform were to be made, the Lord of Kappel appeared as a member of the committees preparing the decisions. But even where he did not act as a spiritual councillor, but as a Cistercian abbot, traces of the Reformation can soon be found. By virtue of his office, the Abbot of Kappel was the visitor of the two female Cistercian convents of Frauenthal and Tänikon¹⁴⁰ – with results that were entirely in line with the Zurich Reformation: by the summer of 1526, for example, most of the Cistercian nuns of Frauenthal had left the convent and married, and between April and July 1528 the convent was transferred to the city of Zug¹⁴¹. The exchange between Frauenthal and Kappel does not seem to have been limited to purely administrative matters. Around 1525, Bullinger dedicated his vernacular interpretation of Romans 1–5 to the Cistercian nuns Verena Huser and Anne Kolin of Frauenthal¹⁴², after having already sent them his 1524 treatise *Von dem namen Christi unseren seligmachers (On the Name of Christ Our Saviour)*¹⁴³, and, prior to that, probably also two other (now lost) texts¹⁴⁴. As Susi Hausamman suggests in her

¹³⁷ Egli, *Actensammlung*, 577 [no. 1330]; see Bullinger, *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 428. In his letter to Vadian dated 16 May 1527, Joner had already had to decline an invitation to St. Gallen, citing health reasons that required him to take a spa cure (see *VBS*, vol. 4, 59 [no. 485]).

¹³⁸ See *Regesten der Cistercienser-Abtei Cappel*, 31 [no. 370]; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 288.

¹³⁹ Bullinger, *Diarium*, 12; id., *Reformationsgeschichte*, vol. 1, 94.

¹⁴⁰ See Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 246.

¹⁴¹ See Eugen Gruber and Cécile Sommer-Ramer, *Frauenthal*, in *Helvetia Sacra*, vol. 3/3.2, Bern 1982, 709–727, here 711, note 40 and 720; see Locher, *Reformation*, 424; *HBBW*, vol. 1, 48, note 4; Staedtke, *Kanton Zug*, 43; Egli, *Reformation*, 80.

¹⁴² Heinrich Bullinger, *Vorlesung über den Römerbrief (1525)*, in *HBTS*, vol. 2, 21–132, here 21. On Bullinger's connections to Frauenthal, see in particular Staedtke, *Kanton Zug*, 43–45.

¹⁴³ See *ibid.*, 44; see also Willy Brändli, *Peter Kolin von Zug*, in *Zwingliana* 9/3, 1950, 150–171, on Bullinger's relationship with the Kolin family, although Brändli moves on from Anna to Peter Kolin far too quickly.

¹⁴⁴ See Hausamman, *Römerbriefauslegung*, 32.

careful study of Bullinger's early lectures on the Epistle to the Romans, Abbot Wolfgang may have encouraged Bullinger to support the spiritual care of the Frauenthal nuns by sending them his writings¹⁴⁵.

Early on, the contacts that existed between Kappel and the Cistercian convent of Tänikon in Thurgau, based on the supervisory rights of the abbot of Kappel, also seem to have brought reformatory ideas to this women's convent¹⁴⁶. As early as September 1523, the Thurgau bailiff complained that Kappel monks were encouraging their sisters in the Order to leave the convent and enter into marriage, and that the visitor who had come to Tänikon on behalf of the abbot had even himself taken a nun as his wife¹⁴⁷. In 1524, there were also several reports of nuns leaving their convent¹⁴⁸. Abbot Wolfgang, it appears, made deliberative use of his position as father abbot and visitor of the Cistercian nuns of Tänikon to give them reformist impetus by sending like-minded monks from Kappel there. An inventory of the Cistercian convent in Tänikon, dated 2 October 1529 and written by Abbot Wolfgang, had become necessary because nine of the 13 convent women who were still in the convent apart from the abbess had already left and were demanding a dowry, two more women were willing to leave, and Abbess Anna Wälter von Blidegg herself wanted to leave the convent and go to Zurich; only two Cistercian nuns apparently wished to remain in the convent¹⁴⁹. The fact that Joner compiled this inventory is remarkable in that research generally assumes that the Council of Zurich had taken over the rights of the Kappel monastery in Tänikon after its handover¹⁵⁰. However, the Zurich authorities apparently made use of Joner's powers in this case as well, so that he exercised them on behalf of Zurich within the scope of his traditional powers as supervisor of the administration of the Tänikon monastery.

¹⁴⁵ *Ibid.*, 33.

¹⁴⁶ See Largiadèr, *Papsturkunden*, no. 59 (order to the abbot of Kappel to incorporate Tänikon into the Cistercian Order and grant him the right of visitation, 1249); no. 62 (order for the incorporation of Tänikon into the Cistercian Order by the abbot of Kappel or a neighbouring monastery, 1250); no. 78 (transfer of the administration of the sacraments and visitation to the abbot of Kappel at the request of the sisters, 1257), as well as Elisabeth Meyer-Marthaler, *Tänikon*, in *Helvetia Sacra*, vol. 3/3.2, 917–950, here 919; see also Alfred L. Knittel, *Die Reformation im Thurgau*, Frauenfeld 1929, 54.

¹⁴⁷ The report by Landvogt Niklaus Muheim dated 27 September 1523 is reproduced by *Die Eidgenössischen Abschiede aus dem Zeitraume von 1521 bis 1528*, in Johannes Strickler (ed.), *Amtliche Sammlung der ältern Eidgenössischen Abschiede [EA]*, vol. 4.1a, Brugg 1873, 331 [no. 155, addendum to a and b, item 2]; see Knittel, *Reformation*, 52 and 54.

¹⁴⁸ See the report of the Thurgau bailiff to the Diet on 3–4 September 1524 in Baden, in *EA*, vol. 4.1a, 487 [no. 207c]; see Knittel, *Reformation*, 56; Meyer-Marthaler, *Tänikon*, 921.

¹⁴⁹ *ASchweizerRef*, vol. 2, 329 [no. 855] (inventory); see Knittel, *Reformation*, 51–56; Egli, *Reformation*, 80; Bless-Grabher, *Kappel*, 261; *HBBW*, vol. 1, 57, note 1.

¹⁵⁰ According to Meyer-Marthaler, *Tänikon*, 921.

Abbot Wolfgang was apparently present when the Reformation was introduced in August 1529 at the Cistercian monastery in Wettingen under Georg Müller, who succeeded Abbot Andreas Wengi¹⁵¹. As Jakob Löw, the Wettingen steward in Basel, wrote to Zwingli on 15 August 1529 to ask him to support him and Müller in Basel in the negotiations on the introduction of the Reformation in the monastery and village of Wettingen, he and Müller had « also, when we left you, sent word to the lord of Kappel, who will also come. So we trust in God that he will reveal his holy word to us¹⁵² ». Löw and Abbot Müller therefore assumed that the abbot of Kappel would also make his expertise available to his fellow monks in Wettingen. As a report by Niklaus Manuel dated 8 August 1529 to the mayor and council of Bern shows, the decision to introduce the Reformation in the monastery of Wettingen had already been made in principle at that time¹⁵³, so the visit by Abbot Wolfgang and Zwingli was most likely concerned with questions of concrete implementation¹⁵⁴. Much like Joner in Kappel, Müller in Wettingen also appears to have retained leadership of the monastery after the introduction of the Reformation¹⁵⁵.

3 Conclusion

At the beginning of this essay, the group of *practitioners of the Reformation* was provisionally defined as comprising (1) clergy with prominent local or regional positions who (2) actively participated in the Reformation's transformation of church structures and institutions not for reasons of expediency but because they agreed with its theological content, and who (3) were known less for their own theological writings than for their well-documented involvement in the concrete processes of preparing

¹⁵¹ See André Hägler and Anton Kottmann, *Wettingen*, in *Helvetica Sacra*, vol. 3/3.1, 425–491, here 432, 462.

¹⁵² *Jakob Löw to Zwingli*, 15 August 1529, in Z X, 272 [no. 902], here 272,1–3; see *HBBW*, vol. 1, 48, note 4; Egli, *Reformation*, 79.

¹⁵³ See Niklaus Manuel's report to the Schultheiss and Council of Bern, 8 August 1529, in *EA*, vol. 4.1b, 317 [no. 156, item 1].

¹⁵⁴ This is also suggested by Manuel's report: "Having unanimously agreed, with the exception of one monk, to restore the content of the Holy Word of God in accordance with the content of the reformation of grace with divine assistance, *they obtained a message from the Council of Zurich*" (*EA*, vol. 4.1b, 317 [no. 156, item 1] [emphasis added by T. J.]). On 30 July 1530, the Zurich Council assured the abbot and convent of Wettingen of its support and proposed sending suitable members of the monastery to Zurich to study (see *EA*, vol. 4.1b, 717 [no. 359]).

¹⁵⁵ See Hägler/Kottmann, *Wettingen*, 462. As the results of the Diet in Baden on 5–6 October 1529 show, however, the Confederates kept a close watch on developments; although the administration of the monastery was once again handed over to the abbot and grand chamberlain until further notice, the bailiff's representatives were also commissioned to draw up an inventory (see *EA*, vol. 4.1b, 390 [no. 199k]).

and implementing such changes. It should be clear that Abbot Wolfgang Joner can be considered representative of this group:

- (1) As abbot of Kappel, Wolfgang Joner held a leading position locally within his convent, regionally due to the various secular and ecclesiastical properties and rights of Kappel Monastery, and supra-regionally as father abbot and visitor of two female Cistercian convents. Traditionally guaranteed rights of patronage and appointment enabled him to fill church positions with clergy who were akin to the Reformation. The right to provide pastoral care and visit the Cistercian convents of Frauenthal and Tänikon gave him the opportunity to introduce Reformation ideas into these convents.
- (2) Even though Abbot Wolfgang succeeded in preserving the institutional existence of his monastery for the time being through its reformation and could hope to receive appropriate compensation for his services from the Zurich magistrate, the worsening economic situation of the Kappel convent due to the withdrawal of foundations and the loss of land and rights outside Zurich's sphere of influence suggests that his commitment to the Zurich Reformation was not motivated by economic or political opportunism. Ultimately, the introduction of the Reformation in Kappel accelerated the decline of the monastery and, given its geographically exposed location, led to a constant threat of military attacks from Central Switzerland. Abbot Wolfgang Joner's early support for Zwingli, his employment conditions, his promotion of the young Bullinger, and his active involvement as a preacher suggest that he was in favour of the theological ideas of the Reformation.
- (3) Despite the abbot's prolific preaching activity, which is documented by various sources, no direct written evidence of his theology has survived; it is impossible to determine with certainty to what exact extent the programmatic letter to Asper, written by Bullinger in Abbot Wolfgang's name, reflected the abbot's theological position. On the other hand, Wolfgang Joner's involvement in almost all the important committees appointed by the authorities during the early Zurich Reformation is irrefutably documented; it is also clear *that* he worked as a preacher to spread Reformation theology in the Freiamt region. The same applies to the reforms in Kappel itself and to his involvement in the Reformation of the Cistercian convents of Frauenthal and Tänikon and the Cistercian monastery of Wettingen. Although it is therefore difficult to paint a precise picture of Wolfgang Joner's theology, it can be said that the abbot of Kappel was involved in the most important decisions of the Zurich Reformation. This does not rule out the possibility that he had his own theological profile: the delay with which the Zurich

reform mandates were implemented in Kappel, as well as the advice of the rural prelates in December 1523, which deviated from the position of the city pastors and warned against a hasty abolition of the Mass, point to a very context-sensitive reformatory theology that was keen to preparing changes in church practice through persuasion based on content, thus ensuring the broadest possible consensus.